

Evaluation of Inhibitory Activities of Phytochemicals from Cabbage and Cucumber on Some Common Neurodegenerative Enzymes Using an Experimental Wister Rats Study Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Neurodegenerative diseases are one of the commonest health disorders affecting nerve and brain tissues systems. Conventional health treatment system for these kind of disorders were only limited to management process and most of them are filled with tremendous side effects. These necessitated the evaluation of two commonly consumed natural vegetative leafy plant (cabbage) and fruit crop plant (cucumber) that were articulated to contained a promising phytochemicals with inhibitory activities against such neurodegenerative disorders. This study investigated the inhibitory activities of two commonly consumed natural vegetative crops (cabbage and cucumber) on the activities of some common known neurodegenerative enzymes using animal model (rats) analysis. The data results generated from the research study revealed that both the two vegetative meals (cabbage and cucumber) have significant inhibitory activities on the enzymes associated with neurodegenerative disorders. The results indicated that cabbage and cucumber mixed meal exhibited anti-activities on acetylcholine esterase, butyryl choline esterase, monoamine oxidase, Superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione level, glutathione peroxidase and Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase enzymes with a mean value of 0.9775; 8.5825; 0.1950; 1.4775; 0.3075; 0.7600; 0.5225 and 1.0675; 9.2525; 0.3200; 1.5650; 0.2825; 0.7075; 0.5275 respectively. These showed that both the two vegetative meals (cabbage and cucumber) have inhibitory activities on neurodegenerative enzymes either through preventive or modulation mechanism of neurodegenerative enzymes thereby reducing their neurodegenerative activities. Lastly, evidence from the generated comparison study revealed that cabbage mixed meal had higher efficacy of inhibitory activities over cucumber vegetative mixed meals in management of neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's disease and cholinergic dysfunction.

KEYWORDS: cabbage, cucumber, neurodegenerative enzymes, disorders, inhibitory activities, mixed meals

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I. INTRODUCTION

Neurodegenerative diseases (NDDs) such as dementia, alzheimer's and parkinson's are neuronal disorders that affect central and peripheral nervous systems of the brain, which leads to progressive loss of nerve structure needed for brain functions (Emmanuel, *et al.*, 2022; Youdim and Bakhle, 2006 and Youdim, *et al.*, 2006). Neurodegenerative enzymes such as acetylcholine esterase (Trang and Khandar, 2019; Gohar, *et al.*, 2014; Colovic, *et al.*, 2013), butyryl choline esterase (Trang and Khandar, 2019; Gohar, *et al.*, 2014), monoamine oxidase (Chan, *et al.*, 2011; Youdim and Bakhle, 2006 and Youdim, *et al.*, 2006), superoxide dismutase (Saravana, *et al.*, 2024), glutathione level (Ethan, *et al.*, 2026), glutathione peroxidase (Anna, *et al.*, 2015) and Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase (Xiaoyan, *et al.*, 2022) are the most common causes of 60–70% neurodegenerative disorders in dementia (Pushpa, *et al.*, 2024), alzheimer's (Terry, *et al.*, 2007) and parkinson's diseases (Youdim, *et al.*, 2006). The use of Inhibitory activity therapy on neurodegenerative enzymes for treatment of neurodegenerative disorders in patients is now the new strategic alternative treatment method in medicine (Thi, *et al.*, 2025; Rosaria, *et al.*, 2023; Finberg and Rabey, 2016). Phytochemicals with inhibitory activities to neurodegenerative enzymes are vastly found in vegetative leafy and fruity crop plants (Šučur *et al.*, 2016; Tarozzi, *et al.*, 2013;

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Chen, *et al.*, 2011; Quideau, *et al.*, 2011; Dai and Mumper, 2010; Harrison and May, 2009; Orhan, *et al.*, 2007 and Chen, *et al.*, 2005). Evidences from previous research studies have shown that vegetative leafy and fruity crop plants such as cabbage and cucumber have potential preventive remedies and treatment therapy on neurodegenerative disorders (Subash, *et al.* 2014; Mukherjee, *et al.* 2007).

Cabbage (*Brassica oleraceavar. capitata* L) is a biennial vegetative leafy plant from the genus *Brassica* (Olga, *et al.*, 2024; Zihan, *et al.*, 2024). While, cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.) is a melon vine cylindrical green fruity crop plant from the genus *Cucurbitaceae* family (Jurd, 2009). In Nigeria context, these two vegetative crops are commonly consumed as component of local dietary dishes or medicinal purposes (Deborah, *et al.*, 2025; Taiwo, *et al.*, 2021). As an alternative preventive or treatment options for neurodegenerative disorders from natural products, this research study undertake to evaluate inhibitory activities of phytochemicals from cabbage (*Brassica oleracea*) and cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) on some common neurodegenerative enzymes using animal models study analysis particularly Wister rats (Franco, 2013; Zhao, and Etherton, 2001). The outcome of the research study would provide an invaluable knowledge on neuro-protective or treatment potential of these natural products to neurobiology and therapy. Based on this hypothetical view, this research study explores and evaluates the potential neuroprotective activities of phytochemicals from cabbage and cucumber as an alternative, effective and minimal side effect therapy compared to the use of conventional curative therapy method in treatment of neurodegenerative disorders (Cummings and Zhong, 2006).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Animal Sample Collection

Twelve (12) true breed adult male (120 days old) Wister rats were obtained from animal husbandry, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria. The obtained animals were caged in metallic cage at room temperature (25±5°C), feds using standard animal feed (Chikum, Nig.) and and water for a period of seven (7) days for environmental adaptation and feeding acclimatization prior to start of experimental study.

B. Simulation of Experimental Research Groups

Two experimental research controlled groups, one experimental research cabbage treated animal group, and one experimental research cucumber treated animal groups were simulated and labelled on metallic cages respectively. Each experimental research group contains three adult male Wister rats.

C. Simulation of Experimental Dietary Meal Feeds

Leafy vegetation of cabbage, fruity crop of cucumber and standard animal feed from Chikum (Nig. Ltd) were used to compose and simulate three experimental dietary feeds (controlled feed – containing purely standard animal feed; cabbage treated animal feed – containing minced mixture of cabbage + standard animal feed at 50:50 w/w and cucumber treated animal feed – containing minced mixture of cucumber + standard animal feed at 50:50 w/w respectively. The compositions for each feed are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Compositions in each simulated experimental dietary animal feeds

Compositions	Controlled animal feed	Cabbage treated animal feed (animal feed mixed with cabbage w/w)	Cucumber treated animal feed (animal feed mixed with cucumber w/w)
Crude Protein	21%	10.5%	10.5%
Crude Fat	4%	2%	2%
Crude Fibre	5%	2.5%	2.5%
Calcium	1%	0.5%	0.5%
Phosphorus	0.50%	0.25%	0.25%
Lysine	1.15%	0.575%	0.575%
Methionine	0.50%	0.25%	0.25%
Metabolized energy	2900kcal/kg	1450 kcal/kg	1450 kcal/kg
Coccidiostats	50mg/kg diet	25mg/kg diet	25mg/kg diet

D. Experimental Research Design

The twelve (12) obtained Wister rats were partition into the four labelled experimental research (2 controlled animal; 1 cabbage treated animal and 1 cucumber treated animal) groups respectively. Each experimental research group contains three adult male Wister rats. The four simulated experimental resech groups were fed with dietary feeds accordigly (controlled group with control dietary feed; cabbage treated animal group with cabbage dietary feed and cucumber treated animal group with cucumber dietary

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feed) for a period of 21 days. At interval of 7 days (days 7, 14 and 21), blood samples were collected from each experimental research groups through acuvein processes. Serum samples were generated from the collected blood samples. The obtained serum samples were then evaluated for the activity of some common biochemical neurodegenerative enzymes (acetylcholinesterase, butyrylcholine esterase, monoamine oxidase, superoxidedismutase, glutathione, glutathioneperoxidase and Na⁺/K⁺ATPase) activities respectively.

E. Evaluation of Biochemical Neurodegenerative Enzymes Activities

a. Methodology for Evaluation of Serum Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) Activity

Ellman assay using colorimetric method was therefore used. The assay method evaluates acetylcholinesterase activity in the serum sample and the procedure for the assay analysis was followed as described by Ashwin, (2023).

b. Methodology for Evaluation of Serum Butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) Activity

Ellman assay using spectrophotometric method was therefore used. The assay method evaluates butyrylcholinesterase activity in the serum sample and the procedure for the assay analysis was followed as described by Ashwin, (2023).

c. Methodology for Evaluation of Serum Monoamine Oxidase (MAO) Activity

Continuous assay using spectrophotometric method was therefore used. The assay method evaluates monoamine oxidase activity in the serum sample and the procedure for the assay analysis was followed as described by Andrew, et al. (1997) modified by Rona and Keith (2017).

d. Methodology for Evaluation of Serum Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) Activity

Enzyme assay using xanthine oxidase – NBT method was therefore used. The assay method evaluates superoxide dismutase activity in the serum sample and the procedure for the assay analysis was followed as described by Christine and Joseph, (2010).

e. Methodology for Evaluation of Serum Glutathione Activity

Tietze enzyme assay using spectrophotometric method was therefore used. The assay method evaluates serum glutathione level in the serum sample. The procedure for the assay analysis was followed as described by Irfan, *et al.*, (2006).

f. Methodology for Evaluation of Serum Glutathione Peroxidase Activity

Enzyme assay using xanthine oxidase – NBT method was therefore used. The assay method evaluates Glutathione Peroxidase activity in serum sample and the procedure for the assay analysis was followed as described by Christine and Joseph, (2010), modified by Kshipra, *et al.*, (2017).

g. Methodology for Evaluation of Serum Na⁺/K⁺ATPase Activity

Spectrophotometric assay using Fiske – Subbarow Method was therefore used. The assay method evaluates Na⁺/K⁺ATPase activity in serum sample and the procedure for the assay analysis was followed as described by Abulnaja, *et al.*, (2017).

F. Statistical Data Analysis

Statistical software of Minitab version 7.1 was used to evaluate mean, student t-test and ANOVA test. Statistical significant were achieved and considered when the p-value was (p≤0.05).

III.RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Results

The data results generated after a time course-interval evaluation of inhibitory activities on neurodegenerative enzymes from the four simulated experimental research (controlled animal; cabbage treated animal and cucumber treated animal) groups were presented in table 4.1 and 4.2 below.

Table 4.1: Inhibitory activities on neurodegenerative enzymes as evaluated from time course-interval of cabbage treated experimental research animal group

Biochemical parameters	Control (0-day) Mean(n-3) (U/dl)	Test 1 (3-day) Mean(n-3) (U/dl)	Test 2 (6-day) Mean(n-3) (U/dl)	Test 3 (9-day) Mean(n-3) (U/dl)	STD	Sig (p≤0.05)
Acetylcholinesterase	1.36	1.28	0.19	1.08	0.5380	0.036
Butyryl choline esterase	8.67	8.61	8.58	8.47	0.0838	0.000
Monoamine oxidase	0.26	0.22	0.18	0.12	0.0597	0.007
Superoxidedismutase	1.59	1.53	1.47	1.32	0.1159	0.000
Glutathionelevel	0.39	0.33	0.29	0.22	0.0714	0.003
Glutathioneperoxidase	0.87	0.81	0.74	0.62	0.1074	0.001
Na ⁺ /K ⁺ ATPase	0.68	0.36	0.58	0.47	0.1382	0.005

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Table 4.2: Inhibitory activities on neurodegenerative enzymes as evaluated from time course-interval of cucumber treated experimental research animal group

Biochemical parameters	Control (0-day) Mean(n-3) (U/dl)	Test 1 (3-day) Mean(n-3) (U/dl)	Test 2 (6-day) Mean(n-3) (U/dl)	Test 3 (9-day) Mean(n-3) (U/dl)	STD	Sig (p≤0.05)
Acetylcholineesterase	1.36	1.16	0.97	0.81	0.2260	0.003
Butyryl choline esterase	9.66	9.38	9.11	8.86	0.3448	0.000
Monoamine oxidase	0.46	0.35	0.29	0.18	0.1169	0.012
Superoxidedismutase	1.78	1.64	1.51	1.33	0.1916	0.000
Glutathionelevel	0.45	0.33	0.22	0.13	0.1384	0.027
Glutathioneperoxidase	0.92	0.79	0.64	0.48	0.1900	0.005
Na ⁺ /K ⁺ ATPase	0.73	0.61	0.49	0.28	0.1919	0.012

Statistical data results (means, standard deviations and significance) were evaluated on the above data results in order to evaluate the inhibitory effects of the two vegetative mixed meals (cabbage and cucumber) on the activities of some commonly known neurodegenerative enzymes using animal model study analysis after a time course intervals of treatment period and the evaluated results were presented in table 4.3 and 4.4 below.

The essence of the evaluation study was to demonstrate the statistic insight and relevance of two vegetative mixed meals (cabbage and cucumber) in influencing the inhibitory activities on neurodegenerative enzymes in rat's brain tissues.

Table 4.3: Showing the statistical data results (means; standard deviations and significance) on the inhibitory activities of cabbage mixed meal vegetative phytochemicals on neurodegenerative enzymes in rat's brain tissues.

Parameter	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t-value	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Acetyl Choline Esterase	0.9775	0.5380	0.2690	3.634	3	0.036
Butyryl Choline Esterase	8.5825	0.0838	0.0419	204.796	3	0.000
Monoamine Oxidase	0.1950	0.0597	0.0299	6.530	3	0.007
Superoxide Dismutase	1.4775	0.1159	0.0579	25.504	3	0.000
Glutathione Level	0.3075	0.0714	0.0357	8.619	3	0.003
Glutathione Peroxidase	0.7600	0.1074	0.0537	14.154	3	0.001
Na ⁺ /K ⁺ ATPase	0.5225	0.1382	0.0691	7.563	3	0.005

Note: Significant at (p≤0.05), T means Student T-test, df means degrees of freedom

The analysis indicates a significant differences in all the evaluated parameters at p-values (≤0.05). This indicated that the administration of cabbage mixed meal played a significant inhibitory activity on neurodegenerative enzymes in rat's brain tissues.

Table 4.4: Showing the statistical data results (means; standard deviations and significance) on the inhibitory activities of

Parameter	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t-value	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Acetyl Choline Esterase	1.0675	0.2260	0.1130	9.445	3	0.003
Butyryl Choline Esterase	9.2525	0.3448	0.1724	53.668	3	0.000
Monoamine Oxidase	0.3200	0.1169	0.0585	5.475	3	0.012
Superoxide Dismutase	1.5650	0.1916	0.0958	16.338	3	0.000
Glutathione Level	0.2825	0.1384	0.0692	4.082	3	0.027
Glutathione Peroxidase	0.7075	0.1900	0.0950	7.448	3	0.005
Na ⁺ /K ⁺ ATPase	0.5275	0.1919	0.0959	5.498	3	0.012

cucumber mixed meal vegetative phytochemicals on neurodegenerative enzymes in rat's brain tissues.

Note: Significant at (p≤0.05), T means Student T-test, df means degrees of freed

Similarly the analysis indicates significant differences in all the evaluated parameters at p-values (≤0.05). This indicated that the administration of cucumber mixed meal played a significant inhibitory activity on neurodegenerative enzymes in rat's brain tissues.

The data results generated from the comparison analysis of inhibitory effects between the two vegetative mixed meals (cabbage and cucumber) on the activities of some commonly known neurodegenerative enzymes was presented in figure 4.1 below

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Figure 4.1: Showing the comparison analysis of inhibitory effects between the two vegetative mixed meals (cabbage and cucumber) on the activities of some commonly known neurodegenerative enzymes in played a significant inhibitory activity on neurodegenerative enzymes in rat's brain tissues.

B. DISCUSSIONS

The data results generated in table 4.1 and 4.2 above had both revealed that the two vegetative meals (cabbage and cucumber) played a significant inhibitory activities on some commonly known neurodegenerative enzymes that were associated with cholinergic signaling and oxidative stress management at significance p-value ($p \leq 0.05$).

Moreover, The data results generated from the comparison of mean data results (table 4.3 and 4.4) between the two vegetative mixed meals (cabbage and cucumber) on the activities of some commonly known neurodegenerative enzymes had shown that cabbage mixed meal exhibited anti-activities of acetylcholine esterase, butyryl choline esterase, monoamine oxidase, Superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione level, glutathione peroxidase, and Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase enzymes with a mean value of 0.9775; 8.5825; 0.1950; 1.4775; 0.3075; 0.7600 and 0.5225 while cucumber mixed meal exhibited anti-activities of acetylcholine esterase, butyryl choline esterase, monoamine oxidase, Superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione level, glutathione peroxidase, and Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase enzymes with a mean value of 1.0675; 9.2525; 0.3200; 1.5650; 0.2825; 0.7075; 0.5275 respectively (figure 4.1). This indicated that the two vegetative mixed meals (cabbage and cucumber) have cholinergic signaling effects on the neurodegenerative enzymes by reducing thier activities. With these observations it can be deduce that both the two vegetative mixed meals have the potential applications in management as well as preventive therapy of neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's disease and cholinergic dysfunctions.

Moreover, evidence from the generated comparison analysis (figure 4.1) between the two vegetative mixed meals (cabbage and cucumber) on the activities of some commonly known neurodegenerative enzymes had shown that cabbage mixed meal had higher efficacy of inhibitory activities compared to cucumber vegetative mixed meals in management or preventive therapy of neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's disease and cholinergic dysfunction.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusion

The data results generated from this research study had proved that there are compelling evidence that both cabbage and cucumber exert a significant effects on various biochemical parameters related to cholinergic activity and oxidative stress management. The result indicated inhibitory impact on acetylcholine esterase and monoamine oxidase. Reduce activity in these two enzymes as compared to controlled data typically shows the potential of these vegetables as functional foods with neuroprotective and health-promoting properties.

The observed results also indicated inhibitory activity in acetylcholine esterase and monoamine oxidase. This typically suggested that regular consumption of cabbage and cucumber may enhance or improve cholinergic signalings and neurotransmitter balance. This observation is particularly relevant for theraphatic management of patients with neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease, where cholinergic dysfunction and oxidative stress are prevalent. The ability of these vegetables to modulate neurotransmitter metabolism may provide a dietary strategy to support cognitive function, potentially delaying the onset or progression of neurodegenerative conditions.

The significant inhibitory activity of superoxide dismutase and glutathione peroxidase recorded in this study had indicated that both cabbage and cucumber are rich in antioxidants. Antioxidants plays a crucial role in protecting cells from oxidative damage. Oxidative stress is commonly implicated in chronic diseases, including cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, and certain cancers.

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Regular consumption of cabbage and cucumber may enhance the body's antioxidative capacity, this may help in mitigation the effects harmful free radicals that contributed to cellular and tissues damage.

Evidence based on the observations and findings of this study had indicated that incorporation of cabbage and cucumber into the dietary meals may serve as a preventative and therapeutic measure against oxidative stress-related diseases and neurodegenerative conditions. The health benefits associated with cabbage and cucumber are attributed to their rich in phytochemical content, which includes vitamins, minerals, flavonoids, and other bioactive compounds.

Evidence based on the comparative study of this study analysis. It was established and elucidated that cabbage had the high efficacy of dietary interventions in preventive and management therapy of populations at risk for neurodegenerative diseases, cognitive dyfunctions and oxidative stress conditions compared to cucumber dietary intervention.

Lastly, the findings and observations from this study had increase our scientific understanding on the relationships between diets, health and well-being.

B. Recommendations

The observations and findings from this research study's suggested the following recommendations in order to enhance the health benefits associated with the consumption of cabbage and cucumber as mixed meals.

Firstly, it recommend incorporation of cabbage and cucumber daily diets, given their potential neuroprotective and antioxidant properties. Regular consumption can be facilitated through various culinary applications, such as salads, smoothies, and cooked dishes, thereby promoting a versatile and enjoyable dietary intake.

Secondly, the study recommend further research in order to identify and isolate the specific bioactive compounds that were present in cabbage and cucumber and elucidate thier respective contribution to health benefits. This effort would help in development of dietary recommendations of food products in management or preventive therapy of neurodegenerative diseases.

Thirdly, it recomend longitudinal and mechanistic studies in order to evaluate long-term effects of cabbage and cucumber consumption on cognitive function and overall health. Such studies should encompass diverse populations to assess the generalizability of the findings and to account for variations in dietary habits and health outcomes.

Lastily, It recommend indept examination on the effects of different varieties of cabbage and cucumber, preparation methods (raw, cooked, or fermented preparations) in order to determine the optimal form that provide maximal health benefits as well as nutritional value.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No potential evidence of conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Abubakar, M. A., contributed in research design, draft, data evaluations and manuscript write-up. Akinlalu, Y. J. and Mujiburrahman, F. contributed in samples collections, practical evaluations, data collections and computations. Isah, B. I. and Rabiu, S. contributed in statistical analysis. In overall, all authors approved the final version of the paper manuscript.

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